

GREEN PRICING PRACTICES OF SELECTED RESTAURANTS IN QUEZON CITY

John Eldrian Emmanuel Masaga, Hennessy Pucerio, Sean Leonard Salcedo,
Patricia Tabar, Kenneth Tracy Victoria and Dr. John Paul G. Buenaventura

*College of Tourism and Hospitality Management, National University, Sampaloc
Manila, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

The price is what a client must pay to get a product. Many factors, including the cost of the goods, product distinctiveness, competition, and the customer's perception of the product's value, affect a product's price. This research aimed to identify green pricing practices in restaurants. The study applied a mixed method and descriptive method approach with survey questionnaires and interviews. The study used purposive sampling. To collect the data, a survey questionnaire and interview are used, and it's categorized into three parts, with (80) respondents that consist of managers, employees, and customers of selected restaurants in Quezon City. The restaurants are adopting green pricing practices to reduce food and packaging waste and invest in reusable and compostable materials. These strategies differentiate products and cater to changing consumer preferences. The restaurant's commitment to eco-friendly initiatives not only benefits the environment but also enhances menu offerings, appealing to eco-conscious consumers. The perceived value of the product significantly impacts customer satisfaction and propensity to make green purchases. Challenges faced include sourcing sustainable ingredients, investing in eco-friendly packaging, and staff awareness. To overcome these, the restaurants negotiate better terms, invest in compostable packaging, promote green practices through social media, and adjust menu offerings and portions.

Keywords: *Green Pricing, Cost of Product, Product Differentiation, Competition, Customer's Perceived Value of a Product*

INTRODUCTION

As restaurants face rising consumer awareness, stronger regulation, and expanding shareholder demands aimed at maintaining the balance of nature, "green" concerns have grown more important for business decisions (Nguyen-Viet, 2022). Moreover, green restaurants develop as a reaction to the food-service industry's environmental issues, as customers and manufacturers grow more conscious of the implications of food manufacturing on the environment. Green restaurants use ecologically sustainable develops, structures, and operations (Nicolau et al., 2020). Therefore, green practices have been scientifically shown to improve consumers' emotional attachment, contentment, and behaviors that are influencing their desire to purchase and shell out more for green products (Zhang et al., 2021). In addition, collecting and the process of composting as well as energy and water management procedures and the usage of natural foods and materials, have been demonstrated to significantly affect consumer desire to purchase environmentally friendly goods and emotional attachment (Mai et al., 2023). According to the Journal of Economics and Business (JEB) 2023, green pricing practices in the food service sector have been empirically demonstrated to have a substantial influence on consumer intention to purchase and desire to consume green products.

According to Kaur, B. et al., (2022) the term "green price" refers to the setting of prices for environmentally friendly products that may be more expensive than those of conventional non-green products because higher-quality raw materials are used, chemicals and other toxic substances are substituted, and production costs are increased as a result of tighter regulations. Researchers who work with green goods typically use the phrase "premium price" since producing, using, and disposing of green products comes with additional costs, which drive up the cost of production relative to standard non-green products. Furthermore, the implementation of environmental policy measures raises manufacturing costs, which in turn raises the selling price of eco-friendly products. Because green products include eco-friendly properties, consumers.

In developed European nations who support the environment are ready to pay a premium price for them. A product's premium pricing is often seen as an indicator of its superior quality and environmentally friendly attributes. Furthermore, A crucial component of the marketing mix is the green price. If new items are perceived as valuable, the majority of buyers are willing to pay a higher price. Performance, functionality, design, visual appeal, and taste may all be enhanced by this value. The environmental advantages are typically an extra bonus, but they frequently make the difference when comparing the value and caliber of a product with that of a rival. The cost of environmentally friendly products is largely covered by the additional expenses that customers must bear as a result of their superior quality (Yusiana, R. et al., 2019).

Green pricing is a method of setting prices that considers how a good or service will affect the environment. It displays a dedication to sustainability and openness to draw in customers who give environmental conscience top priority when making judgments about what to buy. Green pricing incorporates branding and marketing strategies in

addition to environmental responsibility. Encouraging pricing strategies that prioritize sustainability can draw in an increasing number of environmentally conscientious customers. In addition to helping companies lower their carbon footprint, eco-friendly pricing is a potent marketing tactic. Companies can appeal to environmentally concerned consumers and help create a greener, more sustainable future by developing offset programs, adopting carbon-neutral pricing, and successfully promoting sustainability-focused pricing. The business may lead the green e-commerce revolution if it adopts environmentally friendly pricing. Green pricing is not only a decision in a more eco-aware society, but it is also essential to the long-term viability of enterprises. (Kotomaki, E, 2023). According to Duke and Ateibueri (2022), the underlying idea of green pricing revolves around the price levels that customers are ready to pay to obtain green products and services. A green pricing initiative's performance is determined by a variety of elements. Consumer involvement is critical in the development of an effective strategy; customers must demonstrate their involvement in the idea as well as their readiness to shell out for environmentally more effective utilities. It is important to note that people's comprehension and ability to accept green pricing will vary depending on their financial status and usage; company customers have to be educated that green pricing may benefit their businesses, and others may find it ineffective.

This research aimed to identify green pricing practices in restaurants. While research exists regarding green pricing in restaurants, to overcome the perception-reality gap and advance more in-depth green pricing practices throughout the industry, it underlined how important it is to align marketing messaging with specific sustainable activities. Additionally, it established the significance of green pricing practices in each restaurant in the area. By offering insights into the complexity of green pricing practices, particularly in the setting of Quezon City, this research added to the body of existing literature. The findings of the study can help restaurant establishments learn about green pricing, which will help create knowledge and challenges about green pricing in restaurants in Quezon City and beyond.

By addressing these issues, this research intended to offer food establishments information and suggestions for green pricing practices.

The purpose of the study was to ascertain Quezon City restaurants' green pricing policies.

It specifically aimed to respond to the following questions:

1. What are the green pricing practices of restaurants in terms of:
 - 1.1. Cost of Product
 - 1.2. Product Differentiations
 - 1.3. Competition
 - 1.4. Customer's Perceived Value of Product
2. What challenges do restaurants are facing in implementing and maintaining green pricing practices? How are restaurants responding to these challenges?

METHODOLOGY

The research design used in the study to evaluate the green pricing policies of particular Quezon City restaurants is the descriptive method of research. Descriptive research methods are employed by researchers to obtain knowledge about a certain population or issue. The research also employs a mixed method design, which is a simple approach in which the primary and auxiliary elements come from the same paradigm and can be either qualitative or quantitative. This study offers a thorough and precise understanding of a certain population or the traits and actions of the participants. Descriptive research offers valuable insights that may stimulate further study by gathering and analyzing data on a certain topic. It also aids in the comprehension of the topic by scholars. This approach can be helpful when examining anthropological circumstances where an intuitive approach to meaning finding can be beneficial. The respondents of this study were composed of (2) Managers, (10) employee, and (68) customers of two selected restaurants in Quezon City with a total of 80 respondents. (70) respondent for quantitative questions and (10) respondent for qualitative question. Before the instrument was used in the study, a survey questionnaire was divided into three parts in the order of Part I, the respondent demographic profile is examined to assess the participant's qualifications. The evaluation of the restaurants' green pricing policies is covered in Part II. Five-point Likert scales were employed by the researchers to assess green pricing methods. A 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (not practiced) to 5 (very practiced), will be used to answer the questions. Part III is about the challenges encountered by two selected restaurants in Quezon City in implementing green pricing practices, and it follows the questions about how they address these challenges. The question in Part III will be answered in open-ended writing in order to obtain insights into the challenges met by the restaurants in the implementation of their green pricing practices.

The data gathered from the survey questions will be totalled, noted, and analysed by the researchers. To accurately evaluate the findings of the data analysis and their applicability to the primary goal of the research, the frequency and percentage will also be computed, along with the overall results and final rankings of the criteria contained in the survey questionnaires. The statistical techniques utilized for data interpretation are percentage, frequency, weighted mean, ranking, and likert scale.

Percentage In the respondent profile, a percentage is utilized to ascertain how one component relates to the entire.

Formula: $P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$

N

Where:

f = frequency

N = Number of cases

P = Percentage

Frequency. is the actual response that a respondent makes to a particular item or question on the questionnaire where options are presented.

Weighted Mean. Its purpose is to combine a series of scores. It's the average that's been calculated by assigning different weights to various individual variables.

$$\text{Formula: } WM = \frac{\sum (W_1f_1 + W_2f_2 \dots + w_n f_n)}{N}$$

Where:

WM = weighted mean

f1 = frequency of first cell

w1 = weight of first cell

f2 = frequency of second cell

w2 = weight of second cell

n = number of cases

Ranking. is employed to ascertain the order of variables with increasing and decreasing magnitude. Rank has the highest frequency, with one being the highest and decreasing to the final number.

Likert Scale. The Five (5) Likert Scale Method was employed as the criterion for data interpretation.

The idea of number limitation will be employed as follows:

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.2 – 5.00	Highly Practiced	HP
4	3.3 – 4.19	Practiced	P
3	2.6 – 3.39	Moderately Practiced	MP
2	1.8 – 2.59	Least Practiced	LP
1	1.0 – 1.79	Not Practiced	NP

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sub Problem No. 1 Green Pricing Practices of Restaurant

Table 1

Assessment on Green Pricing Practices of Restaurant in terms of Cost of Product

Cost of Product	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The restaurant's menu design spans a variety of dishes.	4.45	Highly Practiced	4
2. The Restaurant implements strict portion control measures to ensure customers get the right amount of food.	4.46	Highly Practiced	3
3. The restaurant implements a waste reduction program to minimize food and packaging waste.	4.58	Highly Practiced	1
4. The restaurant adopts reducing meat consumption and they are incorporating more plant-based options to cut down on high costs.	3.9	Practiced	5
5. The restaurant is investing in reusable or compostable serving materials to reduce disposable packaging expenses.	4.51	Highly Practiced	2
General Weighted Mean	4.38	Highly Practiced	

Table 1 showed that all five (5) indicators under the cost of product had a grand mean of 4.38 (highly practiced), which comes from the variety of dishes (4.45, highly practiced), implementation of strict portion control measures (4.46, highly practiced), implementation of food and packaging waste reduction (4.48, highly practiced), using more plant-based options to lower the price (3.9, practiced), and investing in reusable serving material (4.51, highly practiced).

The results have shown that the two restaurants with green pricing practices in terms of the cost of the product are using a policy or program to reduce food and packaging waste and investing in reusable and compostable serving material. From this,

a conclusion can be drawn that using an eco-friendly product will cause an expensive price that is reasonable for the customers to buy from the restaurant. Relative to the findings from the Journal of Economics and Business (2023), green materials may be expensive in the restaurant sector. Several green practices, including composting and recycling, sustainable energy and water management, and the procurement of naturally produced food-green goods and materials, have a favorable influence on consumer interest in purchasing green products.

Table 2

Assessment on Green Pricing Practices of Restaurant in terms of Product Differentiation.

Product Differentiation	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The restaurant is offering a unique tasting menu featuring seasonal and sustainable dishes.	4.38	Highly Practiced	1
2. The restaurant is launching plant-based or vegan menus to cater to environmentally conscious diners.	4.03	Practiced	5
3. The restaurant is committed in showcasing sustainability through eco-themed decor.	4.35	Highly Practiced	2
4. The restaurant created a “farm-to-table” menu that highlights locally sourced ingredients.	4.23	Highly Practiced	4
5. The restaurant is offering a “green dining experience” package including a tour of the restaurant.	4.26	Highly Practiced	3
General Weighted Mean	4.25	Highly Practiced	

Table 2 showed that all five (5) questions under the product differentiation variable had a grand total mean of 4.25, indicating that most of the techniques are highly practiced and have an average mean greater than 4.20. Meanwhile, the plant-based or vegan menu for environmentally conscious diners obtained an average mean of 4.03, which falls under the practiced level. This clearly shows that recognizing and carrying out strategies in

relation to product differentiation in green pricing provides a competitive advantage in the field of green consumption.

The results showed that by providing distinctive products that adapt to changing consumer demands, green pricing techniques help differentiate products. But the number of competing items in the restaurant sector has increased significantly, raising the possibility that a product may become lost in the crowd and never find enough traction to thrive. According to ProductPlan (2023), companies use the strategy of "product differentiation" to distinguish one good or service from similar ones that are available in the market. Businesses aim to gain a competitive edge by using compelling, unique selling propositions (USPs) to set their product apart from competitors.

Table 3

Assessment on Green Pricing Practices of Restaurant in terms of Competition

Competition	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The restaurant is actively engaging with environmental organizations to support conservation initiatives	4.29	Highly Practiced	3
2. The restaurant is committed to zero-waste practices, setting an example for competitors.	4.45	Highly Practiced	1
3. The restaurant is updated with the latest sustainable trends, and they incorporate them into the menu.	4.31	Highly Practiced	2
4. The restaurant shares its sustainability journey through social media and marketing campaigns.	4.18	Practiced	5
5. The restaurant is sourcing from unique suppliers that specialize in sustainable or rare ingredients.	4.28	Highly Practiced	4
General Weighted Mean	4.3	Highly Practiced	

Based on the findings from Table 3, the restaurant under study is highly committed to practicing green and sustainable initiatives. The data shows that the restaurant actively engages with environmental organizations to support conservation efforts, scores high in commitment to zero-waste practices, and stays updated with the latest sustainable trends, incorporating them into their menu offerings. Additionally, the restaurant shares its sustainability journey through social media and marketing campaigns, further emphasizing its dedication to environmental responsibility. Moreover, the restaurant demonstrates a commitment to sourcing from unique suppliers specializing in sustainable or rare ingredients. Overall, the grand mean score of 4.3 indicates that the restaurant is highly practiced in its green practices, setting a commendable example for its competitors.

The results indicate that the restaurant is highly dedicated to implementing eco-friendly initiatives within its operations, this partnership showcases the restaurant's commitment to supporting environmental causes and making a positive impact on the community. These findings suggest that restaurants are not only focused on profit but also value sustainability and environmental stewardship. Not only does this benefit the environment but it enhances the menu offerings, making them appealing to eco-conscious consumers. The outcomes highlight the importance of the business aligning with green initiatives for the betterment of the environment. In order to stay competitive, restaurant operations can adopt responsible steps such as implementing recycling policies and preemptive measures to reduce food loss and waste generation. In summary, this work suggests that there is room for regulators and legislators to support hospitality professionals in adopting circular economy strategies and to provide them with financial incentives to reduce food waste in the context of commercial competitiveness. (Mark 2021).

Table 4

Assessment on Green Pricing Practices of Restaurant in terms of Customer's Perceived Value of Product

Customer's Perceived Value of Product	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The restaurant conducts a regular sustainability survey to collect thoughts and show responsiveness to customer concerns.	4.25	Highly Practiced	2
2. The restaurant is sharing stories and experiences of the restaurant's	4.15	Practiced	5

sustainability through newsletters and blogs.			
3. The restaurant is highlighting customer feedback on sustainable practices through social media and testimonials.	4.23	Highly Practiced	3
4. The restaurant provides educational materials on sustainability and sourcing practices.	4.22	Highly Practiced	4
5. The restaurant clearly communicates its sustainability efforts on its menu.	4.28	Highly Practiced	1
General Weighted Mean	4.23	Highly Practiced	4.23

Table 4 shows that the customer's perceived value of product had a total grand mean 4.23, which can be interpreted as (Highly Practiced). As the researchers testified, the restaurant conducts a regular sustainability survey to collect thoughts and show responsiveness to customer concerns (4.25, Highly Practiced), it shares stories of the restaurants sustainability through newsletters and blogs (4.15, Practiced), and it highlights customer feedback on sustainable practices through social media and testimonials (4.23, Highly Practiced), they provide educational materials on sustainability and sourcing practices (4.22, Highly Practiced), and lastly restaurants communicates its sustainability efforts on its menu (4.23, Highly Practiced).

The findings revealed the green pricing practices of the restaurants in terms of customers' perceived value of the product will contribute to the marketing provided based on the wants and expectations that are environmentally conscious. It is used to maintain long-term relationships with the customers. It is possible to conclude that a customer's perceived value significantly impacts their satisfaction level and their propensity to make green purchases. Relative to the findings of Juliana (2020), Customers' evaluation of a market offering's overall value is based on their requirements and expectations; ecologically sustainable needs and expectations are referred to as "green perceived value." Green perceived value is seen as a crucial element in sustaining long-term customer relationships. It also has a significant impact on customer satisfaction and green purchase intentions.

Table 5

Summary Assessment on Green Pricing Practices of Restaurant in terms of the Four (4) Variables in SOP no. 1

Green Practices SOP Variables	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Cost of Product	4.38	Highly Practiced	1
2. Product Differentiation	4.25	Highly Practiced	3
3. Competition	4.3	Highly Practiced	2
4. Customer's Perceived Value of Product	4.23	Highly Practiced	4
General Weighted Mean	4.29	Highly Practiced	

Table 5 shows that the green pricing practices had a general weighted mean of 4.29 which is interpreted as high practice in implementing green pricing practices. The cost of the product has a weighted mean of 4.38 (highly practiced), followed by the product differentiation which has a weighted mean of 4.25 (highly practiced), competition has a weighted mean of 4.3 (highly practiced, and lastly the customer's perceived value of product which has a weighted of 4.23 (highly practiced).

Sub Problem No. 2 Challenges of the restaurants in implementing and maintaining green pricing practices? How are restaurants responding to these challenges?

Table 6

Challenges

Challenges	Responding to the Challenges	Response
<i>Sourcing sustainable ingredients</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Supplier Assessment</i> • <i>Negotiate better terms</i> • <i>Build long lasting relationship with suppliers</i> • <i>Diversified ingredient sourcing</i> • <i>Menu engineering strategies</i> • <i>Adapting flexible menu that prioritize locally ingredients</i> 	R1, R2, R3, R4, R6, R10

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Adjusting price</i> 	
<i>Eco-friendly packaging</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Compostable containers</i> • <i>Recyclable material</i> • <i>Encouraging customers to opt for dine-in</i> 	R1, R3, R9
<i>Staff and consumer awareness for green activities</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Highlighting menu description</i> • <i>Social media marketing</i> • <i>Signage</i> • <i>Training programs to raise awareness among employee</i> 	R5, R8
<i>Higher cost sourcing sustainable ingredients</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Adjusting portion size</i> • <i>Adjusting menu offerings</i> 	R7

R = Respondent - N = 10

Table 6 showed the tabular presentation of challenges of the restaurants in implementing and maintaining green pricing practices and how are restaurants responding to these challenges. The respondent is having challenges in sourcing sustainable ingredients, investing in eco-friendly packaging, and staff and customer awareness for green practices. The findings showed that they responded to the challenges by negotiating better terms and long-lasting relations with the suppliers, investing in compostable or recyclable packaging, social media marketing to the awareness of the customers that the restaurant is implementing green practices, training programs for the employees to make them aware of the importance of green practices, and lastly adjusting the menu offerings and portion.

Conclusions

1. Among the five indicators in product cost, implementing waste reduction of food and packaging waste got the highest ranking while reducing meat consumption was the lowest. Moreover, the study found that green pricing practices are highly practiced, with respondents valuing their implementation in terms of product costs.
2. The respondents believed that all indicators concerning green pricing methods in terms of product differentiation are highly practiced. This indicates that implementing a unique tasting menu as the highest and plant-based or vegan products as the lowest can differentiate products that can be an advantage in the competitive market.

3. Based on the conducted survey, all indicators on the assessment of green pricing strategies in terms of competition are highly practiced. It's implementing zero-waste initiatives has the highest interpretation while being transparent and proactive about its sustainability initiatives with the lowest grand mean. The restaurant communicates its sustainability efforts on the menu to present good perceptions of the customer's value of the products. This green perceived value is a crucial aspect of customer satisfaction and purchase intentions, as it influences their evaluation of a market offering based on their environmentally sustainable needs.
4. The five indicators of customer's perceived value of product received a highly practiced based on the evaluation of the respondents, the restaurant communicates its sustainability efforts on its menu has the highest interpretation while the restaurants that share stories and experiences of the restaurant's sustainability through newsletters and blogs got the lowest interpretation.
5. The company faces challenges in sourcing sustainable ingredients and packaging due to seasonal changes, supplier shortages, and consumer and staff awareness about green practices. Despite these challenges, the company is committed to creating sustainable solutions. The respondent addressing the challenges by diversifies their ingredient sources, implement menu engineering strategies, and invest in recyclable packaging. They also start composting initiatives and negotiate better terms with suppliers. They leverage economies of scale to lower prices and stabilize the supply chain. They explore local suppliers and adjust their menu to highlight environmentally friendly ingredients without compromising flavor and quality. They increase plant-based options and implement training programs to promote sustainability through menu descriptions, social media marketing, and signage.

Recommendations

The study's suggestions are as follows, based on its results and conclusions.

1. In terms of reducing meat consumption, restaurants should use plant-based food as an alternative ingredient for the specific product that will engage more health-conscious customers. Although the price may have increased from before, most customers will be satisfied with these changes because of the alternative plant-based ingredients.
2. The restaurant should think about using seasonal ingredients or introducing one-time specials to effectively set itself apart from the competition and excite customers. Additionally, asking customers for feedback or conducting surveys can give the restaurant important insights into their preferences and help them create new products that will suit their changing needs and tastes. Furthermore, using innovative marketing strategies to draw attention to the special qualities and advantages of these new products can help create excitement and increase consumer interest and engagement.

3. To obtain a competitive edge, restaurants need to offer distinctive items to set themselves apart from rivals, adjust to their surroundings, and encourage innovation. Restaurants ought to concentrate on creating eco-friendly products that will appeal to customers that care about the environment as well. This can be accomplished by forming alliances with suppliers who are dedicated to sustainability and who hold similar values. Additionally, by promoting an innovative culture within their companies, they may consistently enhance their green pricing tactics and obtain a competitive advantage in the marketplace.
4. In terms of customer perceptions can be significantly impacted by how reliable and credible the source providing green pricing suggestions is. The restaurant should communicate regarding how goods and services affect the environment can boost confidence and improve consumer perception. Also, reassure customers that dining at a restaurant with green pricing means not compromising quality or taste. Emphasize any positive reviews or awards the business has received for its food to reassure customers that they will have a satisfying meal.
5. The restaurants should continue to develop their product offering by using sustainable ingredients. By partnering with a local supplier and having a long-term relationship, they may reduce the cost of materials and offer an affordable but quality product to the customers. Also, they should invest in R&D for sustainable products to have a new offering of dishes and beverages. That way, they may attract more customers, especially environmentally conscious customers.
6. When it comes to implementing green pricing practices in restaurants, the challenges of finding reliable suppliers and training employees in green marketing can indeed be tough. To address the issue of sourcing reliable suppliers, restaurants can consider building long-term relationships with vendors who are transparent about sustainable practices. This could involve conducting thorough research, requesting certifications, and visiting supplier facilities when possible.
7. It's crucial to give staff members thorough training on the advantages of sustainability, how it fits with the restaurant's values, and how to properly explain these practices to patrons in order to prepare them for green pricing and marketing. Providing practical workshops, disseminating success stories, and rewarding employee involvement are further strategies for cultivating a sustainable culture in restaurants.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research study holds itself accountable for any issues or rules of ethics that arose throughout the procedure. The instruments utilized during this research were examined and authorized by the researcher's adviser. The researchers distributed survey and interview questionnaires based on the statement of the problem. Participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It will be the participant's personal decision whether to participate or not. The respondents were allowed to demonstrate their collaboration by signing the researcher's permission form, confirming they had fully comprehended the

survey and interview criteria, and agreeing to complete the surveys and interviews that were provided to participants. The permission form outlined the goals and objectives for carrying out a survey and interview that benefits the research, as well as a pledge to keep every participant's confidential data concealed. This study has no potential risks but will be beneficial in the field of hospitality education and the industry.

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